

The impact of molecular data on the phylogenetic position of the putative oldest crown crocodylian and the age of the clade

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Supplementary File 4

Parsimony Morphology Only - modified NM dataset

Figure S1. Parsimony Analysis Morphology Only, modified NM dataset. Strict consensus of 11160 most-parsimonious trees. Numbers on nodes indicate GC Bootstrap values (50% cut).

Undated Bayesian Morphology Only

Figure S2. Morphology Only, Undated Bayesian Analysis. Original NM dataset. Majority-rule consensus of sampled post-brunin trees, with clade posterior probabilities at nodes.

Undated Bayesian Morphology Only - modified NM dataset

Figure S3. Morphology Only, Undated Bayesian Analysis. Modified NM dataset. Majority-rule consensus of sampled post-brunin trees, with clade posterior probabilities at nodes.

Parsimony Molecular Scaffold

Figure S4. Parsimony Analysis, Molecular Scaffold on original NM dataset. Strict consensus of 10000 most-parsimonious trees. Numbers on nodes indicate GC Bootstrap values (50% cut).

Parsimony Molecular Scaffold - modified NM dataset

Figure S5. Parsimony Analysis, Molecular Scaffold on modified NM dataset. Strict consensus of 10000 most-parsimonious trees. Numbers on nodes indicate GC Bootstrap values (50% cut).

Parsimony DNA + Morphology

Figure S6. Morphology and Molecules, Parsimony Analysis of original NM dataset. Strict consensus of 10000 most-parsimonious trees of length 5485. Numbers on nodes indicate GC Bootstrap values (50% cut).

Parsimony DNA + Morphology - modified NM dataset

Figure S7. Morphology and Molecules, Parsimony Analysis of modified NM dataset. Strict consensus of 10000 most-parsimonious trees of length 5483. Numbers on nodes indicate GC Bootstrap values (50% cut).

Bayesian DNA + Morphology

Figure S8. Morphology and Molecules, Undated Bayesian Analysis of original NM dataset. Majority-rule consensus of sampled post-burnin trees, with clad posterior probabilities at nodes.

Bayesian DNA + Morphology - modified NM dataset

Figure S9. Morphology and Molecules, Undated Bayesian Analysis of modified NM dataset. Majority-rule consensus of sampled post-burnin trees, with clade posterior probabilities at nodes.

DNA + Morphology: Tip-Dated

Figure S10. Morphology and Molecules, Tip-Dated Bayesian Analysis. Original NM dataset. Maximum clade credibility consensus of sampled post-burnin trees. Node information includes clade posterior probability (number) and 95% HPD for age estimate (blue bar).

DNA + Morphology: Tip-Dated, modified NM dataset

Figure S11. Morphology and Molecules, Tip-Dated Bayesian Analysis. Modified NM dataset. Maximum clade credibility consensus of sampled post-burnin trees. Node information includes clade posterior probability (number) and 95% HPD for age estimate (blue bar).

Bayesian Reduced taxon consensus tree

Figure S12. Reduced taxon majority-rule consensus tree, Undated Bayesian Analysis, original NM dataset. Values indicate node support based on posterior probability, showing high support of *Portugalosuchus azenhae* outside Crocodylia.

Bayesian Reduced taxon consensus tree - modified NM

Figure S13. Reduced taxon majority-rule consensus tree, Undated Bayesian Analysis, modified NM dataset. Values indicate node support based on posterior probability, showing high support of *Portugalosuchus azenhae* outside Crocodylia.

Parsimony Turner (2015) dataset + *Portugalosuchus*

Figure S14. Parsimony Analysis, addition of *Portugalosuchus azenhae* to Turner (2015) dataset (as in Mateus et al., 2019). One of the 660 most-parsimonious trees.

Parsimony Molecular Scaffold - Blanco (2021) dataset

Figure S15. Parsimony Analysis, Molecular Scaffold on Blanco (2021) dataset. Strict consensus of 3600 most-parsimonious trees.